

Redox Titrations in Non-aqueous Solvents. Determination of Mercaptans, Dithiocarbamates and Xanthates

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Titrimetric procedures, with a visual or potentiometric control of the end point, are described for the determination of mercaptans with iodine monochloride, iodine trichloride, iodobenzene dichloride and N-bromosuccinimide in a mixed solvent of acetonitrile-methanol, and with iodine cyanide, diacetoxy iodobenzene and chloramine-T in acetic acid-methanol. Dithiocarbamates and xanthates are determined with iodine monochloride, iodine trichloride and iodobenzene dichloride in acetonitrile-methanol. Non-aqueous solutions of the oxidizing agents are stable. The procedures are rapid and accurate to 0.1% with a precision of 0.2%. Hydrogen sulphide and thiocarbonyl compounds interfere. Methanol accelerates the oxidation which is otherwise slow in anhydrous acetic acid or acetonitrile. A molecular complex that is formed in the latter solvents is supposed to be broken by methanol.

THE number of redox titrations in non-aqueous media for the determination of organic compounds via functional groups is relatively small. The realization of the theoretical possibilities offered by non-aqueous solutions is reflected by the great variety of acid-base titrations in such media. The use of non-aqueous solvents as media for redox titrations is limited by the lack of oxidizing titrants of suitable stability. The availability of such titrant-solvent systems will lead to the employment of redox titrations for compounds insoluble or unstable in aqueous medium.

The present work was undertaken with a view to test the applicability of some oxidizing agents in the determination of certain sulphur-containing functional groups in non-aqueous solvents. The determination of mercaptans with cupric oleate in 1933 by Bond¹ was probably the first non-aqueous redox titration. This method was later modified by Turk and Reid² who employed cupric alkyl-phthalates in hydrocarbons. Use is also made of cupric perchlorate in acetonitrile to titrate thiourea and ethyl xanthate^{3,4}, of cupric sulphate in dimethylformamide and ferric chloride in pyridine for some mercaptans⁵. Cupric, chromate, ferric and mercuric ions in dimethylformamide solutions have been evaluated for their analytical potential⁶. Lead tetraacetate in anhydrous acetic acid was used for the determination of mercaptans^{7,8} and phenyl thioureas⁹. Acetonitrile solution of ammonium ceric nitrate was found suitable to titrate xanthates¹⁰ and thiourea and its alkyl derivatives¹¹. Recently, N-bromosuccinimide is used in acetonitrile for xanthates and dithiocarbamates¹².

In the present paper, procedures are given for the use of iodine monochloride, iodine trichloride and iodobenzene dichloride in acetonitrile-methanol for the determination of mercaptans, dithiocarbamates and

xanthates. Diacetoxy iodobenzene, iodine cyanide and chloramine-T in acetic acid-methanol are used for titrating mercaptans. Acetonitrile and anhydrous acetic acid, owing to their inertness towards oxidizing and reducing agents, are solvents of choice. Methanol can be used as a cosolvent when the oxidizing agent does not react with it.

Experimental

Reagents :

Iodine monochloride, 0.05N solution in acetonitrile, was prepared by dissolving an approximate amount of the commercially available sample.

Iodine trichloride, 0.05N solution in acetonitrile, was prepared by dissolving an approximate amount of the commercially available sample.

Diacetoxy iodobenzene, 0.05N solution in anhydrous acetic acid, was prepared by the method of Pausacker¹³.

N-Bromosuccinimide, 0.05N solution in acetonitrile, was prepared by dissolving with stirring ca. 4.5 g of sample per litre. The insoluble portion of the reagent was filtered off. The solution was kept in the dark.

Iodobenzene dichloride, 0.05N solution in acetonitrile, was prepared by the method as described by Vogel¹⁴.

Chloramine-T, 0.05N solution in methanol, was prepared by dissolving ca. 5.7 g of sample per litre.

Iodine cyanide, 0.05N solution in acetonitrile, was prepared by dissolving ca. 3.8 g of sample¹⁵ per litre. All these oxidant solutions were standardised iodometrically.

Samples :

Most of the mercaptans were received from Messrs Evans Chemicals, New York, and were used as such.

Diethyldithiocarbamate was a commercial product, the rest being prepared by the usual methods^{16,17}.

Xanthates were prepared from the corresponding sodium or potassium alkoxide by reaction with carbon disulphide¹⁸. The product was recrystallized by dissolution in acetone, filtration of any insoluble matter, and precipitation by adding petroleum ether to the filtrate.

All solvents used were reagent grade chemicals.

Procedures :

Titration of mercaptans : A sample containing 0.1-1.0 mequiv of mercapto group is weighed in a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 30 ml of methanol. When diacetoxo iodobenzene, N-bromosuccinimide, chloramine-T, iodobenzene dichloride or iodine trichloride is used as the titrant, about 50 mg potassium iodide is added and the contents of the flask are swirled to dissolve the solid. About 0.5 ml of anhydrous acetic acid is also added when chloramine-T and iodine cyanide are being used. Titration is followed with 0.05N solution of any of above reagents or iodine monochloride, taken in a 10-ml burette graduated to 0.02 ml. The end-point is indicated by the appearance of iodine colour formed by the first drop in excess of the oxidizing agent by reaction with potassium iodide. Sufficient methanol is to be added so that it is about 80% of the total solvent at the end-point.

In potentiometric titrations, the sample is taken in a 100-ml beaker and the procedure for adding reagents is the same. A modified calomel or antimony electrode is used as the reference electrode and a bright platinum wire as the indicator electrode. The end-point is shown by a large potential jump.

Titration of dithiocarbamates and xanthates : A sample is weighed containing 0.1-1.0 mequiv of -CS.SK group and dissolved in 30 ml of methanol. About 50 mg of potassium iodide is added when iodine trichloride or iodobenzene dichloride is used as the titrant. Titration is followed with 0.05N solution of any of the above reagents or iodine monochloride, being delivered from a 10-ml burette graduated to 0.02 ml, to the appearance of iodine colour. Methanol should be about 80% of the total solvent at the end-point.

The method of potentiometric titration is the same as described for mercaptans.

Results and Discussion

Under the described conditions of titration, mercaptans are oxidized to disulphides, dithiocarbamates to thiuram disulphides and xanthates to dixanthogens. Results are given in Table 1 for the determination of mercaptans. The results obtained with seven titrants are compared with those found by mercurimetry¹⁹, lead(IV) titration⁸, alkalimetry²⁰, iodimetry²¹ and copper(II) titration². Table 2 includes the results on the determination of dithiocarbamates and xanthate with three titrants. Results for the purity determination of dithiocarbamates are compared with those obtained by mercurimetry²² and of xanthates by argentimetry²³. From the pooled data it is found that the present methods furnish results which are precise in the range 0.1-0.2%. The results agreed within 0.1% with those found by comparison methods.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCAPTANS

Compound	Purity, %							Comparison method	
	ICl ₃	Chloramine-T	ICI	NBS	PhI(OAc) ₂	ICN	PhICl ₂		
Benzenethiol	98.5	—	—	98.6	98.3	—	98.5	98.4	Alkalimetry
2-Naphthalenethiol	—	99.7	99.9	99.5	—	99.6	—	99.6	Alkalimetry
2-Mercaptoethanol	97.5	97.3	97.3	97.4	97.6	97.4	97.5	97.3	Pb ⁴⁺ titration
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	—	95.2	—	95.0	95.4	—	—	95.5	Hg ²⁺ titration
Mercaptoacetic acid	92.6	92.8	93.0	—	—	—	92.7	92.9	Iodimetry
p-Toluenethiol	—	—	99.7	99.5	—	99.3	—	99.6	Cu ²⁺ titration
p-Chlorobenzenethiol	98.0	97.8	—	98.2	98.5	—	—	98.1	Alkalimetry
2-Mercaptoethylamine	—	95.1	—	95.4	—	—	95.3	95.2	Iodimetry
1-Butanethiol	98.5	98.2	98.0	98.5	98.1	98.0	98.2	98.3	Cu ²⁺ titration
2-Diethylaminoethanethiol	—	99.6	99.4	—	99.4	—	—	99.5	Pb ⁴⁺ titration
Toluene- α -thiol	97.5	—	—	97.2	97.1	—	97.0	97.2	Cu ²⁺ titration
Glycerol-1-thiol	79.1	79.5	79.3	79.0	79.2	79.3	79.3	79.3	Iodimetry

^a Average of 10 determinations.

Organic disulphides, sulphides, *p*-aminobenzoic and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids do not interfere with the procedures. Large amounts (1 mole of reductant : 100 moles of added substance) of carbon disulphide, formic acid and dimethylsulphoxide do not interfere. Thiophene (1 : 18), acetaldehyde (1 : 12) and acetone (1 : 4) cause about 1% high results. Acrylonitrile (1 : 250) gives 1% low results. Serious interference is caused by thiourea and hydrogen sulphide.

In acetonitrile or anhydrous acetic acid alone, or in their mixtures, the reactions are slow and iodine appears during the course of titration. In methanol or in its mixtures with acetonitrile or anhydrous acetic acid containing about 80% of methanol at the end-point, the reactions are instantaneous and the end point can be located accurately. The dependence of oxidation on methanol is apparently environmental rather than stoichiometric.

Danehy²⁴, from a spectrophotometric study, has found that when the ratio of thiol to iodine in glacial acetic acid is sufficiently high the absorption due to iodide is all but completely extinguished and is replaced by a much more intense absorption both in the near ultraviolet and the near infrared. This corresponds to observations in acetonitrile also. It is not the sulphenyl iodide that is formed, as such substances are intensely coloured. The possibilities of the formation of a charge transfer complex between thiol and iodine or initially formed disulphide and iodine, are consistent with the prevailing information on charge transfer complexes of iodine with many compounds.

The effect of methanol in promoting the oxidation can be attributed to its basicity which is responsible for decomposing the molecular complex and for inhibiting the protonation of iodide ion.

If it is the basicity of methanol that breaks the molecular complex and promotes the oxidation then a more basic species could also fulfil the purpose. A reference may be given here of a method that uses pyridine as a catalyst in the titration of some thiols with iodine in benzene medium²⁵.

Dithiocarbamates and xanthates are decomposed by acids to the corresponding amines and alcohols respectively together with carbon disulphide. Because of its solution in acetic acid, diacetoxy iodobenzene could not be used for these compounds. The determination can, however, be made feasible if the reagent solution is prepared in acetonitrile. Chloramine-T and iodine cyanide function only in acidic medium and, therefore, are inapplicable.

All of the reagents used in these studies are of good stability in non-aqueous media. Unlike aqueous solution, *N*-bromosuccinimide in acetonitrile does not liberate molecular bromine even if stored for 5 days at 20°.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF DITHIOCARBAMATES AND XANTHATES

Compounds	Purity, % Present methods ^a			Comparison method	
	ICl ₃	PhICl ₂	ICl		
Diethyldithiocarbamate	75.9	76.0	—	76.3	Hg ²⁺ titration
Di-Isopropylidithiocarbamate	—	87.5	87.2	87.0	Hg ²⁺ "
Di- <i>n</i> -butyldithiocarbamate	91.3	91.0	91.5	91.4	Hg ²⁺ "
Phenylethyldithiocarbamate	—	79.7	79.8	80.0	Hg ²⁺ "
Diamyldithiocarbamate	92.0	91.8	92.2	92.1	Hg ²⁺ "
1-Propylxanthate	97.8	—	98.0	98.1	Ag ⁺ "
Ethylxanthate	90.4	90.2	—	90.0	Ag ⁺ "
1-Butylxanthate	—	94.6	94.4	94.8	Ag ⁺ "
Allylxanthate	—	94.4	94.8	94.5	Ag ⁺ "
Isopropylxanthate	77.7	78.0	—	78.2	Ag ⁺ "
Isoamylxanthate	95.5	—	95.2	95.0	Ag ⁺ "
1-Octylxanthate	—	97.0	97.1	97.3	Ag ⁺ "

^a Average of 8 determinations

Chloramine-T loses titre rapidly in anhydrous acetic acid but is stable in methanol. Iodine monochloride, iodine cyanide and iodine trichloride can be kept indefinitely. Iodobenzene dichloride requires standardization daily and diacetoxy iodobenzene is to be checked after every 3 days.

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